

[Yosef Mystel](#) is the former president of YAM Management, through which he established 24 [nursing homes](#) across Illinois, Indiana, and Texas. Yosef Mystel was instrumental in managing compliance and finance, including negotiations with banks and lenders. Within a few years, his efforts helped the company increase its bottom-line profits by 25 percent.

He currently focuses on [healthcare investment](#) and philanthropy. Additionally, Yosef Mystel participates in multiple community organizations and public programs. For the past decade, he has held a board membership with the Joan Dachs Bais Yaakov, a Jewish elementary school offering faith-based early childhood education. Additionally, he sits on the executive committee for the Agudath Israel of Illinois. For the past 18 years, he has maintained active involvement with The Chicago Center for Torah and Chesed, a synagogue offering community resources and activities.

Recreationally, Yosef Mystel is a fan of professional sports, including baseball, basketball, football, and soccer. He is an avid supporter of Chicago's hometown teams, including the Bulls, Cubs, Whitesox, Bears, and Blackhawks. Yosef Mystel donates heavily to groups such as the Jewish United Fund/Jewish Federation of Metropolitan Chicago (juf.org), a nonprofit organization that connects volunteers who want to help people in need. The organization follows the basic concept of tikkun olam, or repairing the world through community service, action, and social justice. Over the course of his career, Mr. Meystel has also contributed his time and resources to organizations including the Chicago Center for Torah and Chesed, Camp Nageela Midwest, and Madragos.